

Internal Auditing and Inventory Fraud in Public Sector Organizations in FCT – Abuja, Nigeria

Grant, Bestman Ibuchim, Oshi, Joseph E. O. Ph.D and Prof. Ofurum, Clifford O.

University of Port Harcourt Business School Faculty of Management Sciences University of Port Harcourt
Department of Management, FMS, University of Port Harcourt
Department of Accounting, FMS University of Port Harcourt.

Received 21 January, 2025, Accepted 15 February, 2025, Published 25 March 2025

The study examined the effect of Internal Auditing on Inventory fraud in the Nigerian Public Sector with a focus in the federal capital Territory Abuja. The study dimensions were asset inspection and physical inventory theft fraud, document review and ghost inventory fraud. The research provided answers to four questions and tested four null hypotheses. The study sample comprised of 318 staff from the population of The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Abuja, comprising of the National Headquarters and FCT Office. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique to select samples from the population, using the Taro Yameni method. Data for the study was collected through primary and secondary source. Simple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of statistical packages for social science version 23.0. the study found a negative and insignificant effect of internal audit on physical inventory theft fraud. Based on the findings, the study found a negative and insignificant effect of internal Auditing on physical inventory theft fraud. This finding implies that the forensic accounting that is practiced in the study area as led to a decrease in the physical inventory theft fraud but the decrease has been insignificant. Again, the study found a positive and significant effect of internal auditing on ghost inventory fraud, also implying that the internal auditing practiced in the study area has allowed room for a significant increase in ghost inventory fraud. The study therefore, recommended that inventory theft fraud should also be improved upon by putting a little more effort for the effect to become significant. The inventory management recording mechanism should be enhanced to have software that have several ways of detecting ghost entries in order to minimize the occurrence of ghost inventory fraud.

Keywords: Internal Auditing, Inventory Fraud, Nigerian Public Sector, Asset Inspection

INTRODUCTION

Millichamp (1981) notes that the term audit was derived from the latin word Audire" which means to hear. In public or Private organizations, the Government or Business owners appoint certain persons to manage their respective organizations and in due time these managers render what is regarded as Stewardship Accounting, which is viewed by Millichamp, (1993), as the process whereby the managers of a business report or account to the owners of the business.

The report and accounting are usually done by the means of financial statements. Based on the financial statements by managers business owners engage the services of auditors whether internal or external. As such auditing as viewed by Deskera, Niti Samani (2024) is an official examination and verification of a business's

financial records, the main goal of auditing is to make sure that a company's financial statements are accurate and are following regulatory guidelines. Jaydee Reyes (2024) notes some audit procedures which auditors deploy during auditing, these procedures are: Inquiry, Confirmation, Observation, Inspection of Documents, Inspection of Assets, Recalculation, Reperformance etc. Chirantan (2018) notes that inventory fraud involves the theft of physical inventory items and the misstatement of inventory records on a company's financial statements, Robin (2016) further categorizes inventory fraud into Actual physical; Where an asset goes missing causing a smaller number of goods available for sale and loss to company, and Financial Statements; misrepresenting figures in valuation to carry out fake write offs or avoid

write off to mislead shareholders is also a fraud

Statement of the Problem

Inventory fraud which is a type of asset misappropriation fraud is one of the leading cases of fraud in various organizations across the world, which cuts across the public and private sector and has consequently resulted to the loss and misappropriation of organization's asset, this has become a reoccurring problem hence a need to evaluate the effect of auditing on inventory fraud in the Nigerian public sector, this is in line with the 2018 report to the nations on occupational fraud and abuse by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE 2018) noted that of the three primary categories of occupational fraud, asset misappropriations are by far the most common, occurring in 89% of the cases of occupational fraud, this further shows the extent to which asset misappropriation which constitutes Inventory fraud has bedeviled the public and private sectors around the world.

The problem of theft of government property was highlighted by the former minister of finance Kemi Adeosun (News Agency of Nigeria 5 March, 2017); she noted that the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) recovered 40 vehicles from retired directors from the ministry of water resources, also as reported by Daily Independent Newspaper in July 2014, the Nigerian Police Kebbi State Command recovered stolen medical equipment worth N20.8 million and arrested a suspect, Faruk Zaki who is a civil servant in the state Ministry of Health, the Police Public Relations Officer, Kabiru Bawa, told newsmen in Birnin Kebbi that the medical items missing from the store were worth N29.6 million. Raymond, Nwakoby and Okoye (2016) conducted a study on the impact of Forensic Accounting on Combating Fraud in the Nigerian Banking Industry in Akwa Anambara State Nigeria. Their study was Limited to only Awka in Anambara State, this raises an issue as to the generalization of the findings of their study to other states in Nigeria, furthermore their study focused on the Nigerian Banking Industry, which falls within the private sector, the public sector was not considered in this study, these gaps identified will be addressed in this study as I intend to carry out the Study focusing on the Nigerian public sector and also expanding our populations to cover the Federal Capital Territory Abuja.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Internal Auditing on Inventory fraud in the Nigerian Public Sector with a focus in the federal capital Territory Abuja. Specific objectives of the study include, to:

i. assess the effect of asset inspection on physical inventory theft fraud;

- ii. evaluate the effect of document review on ghost inventory fraud; and
- iii. Examine the effect of asset inspection on ghost inventory fraud.
- iv. Determine the impact of document review on physical inventory theft fraud.

Research Questions

The research questions for this study is as captured below:

- i. What is the effect of asset inspection on physical inventory theft fraud?
- ii. To what extent does document review affect ghost inventory fraud?
- iii. What is the effect of asset inspection on ghost inventory fraud?
- iv. What is the impact of document review on physical inventory theft fraud?

Statement of Hypotheses

There are four hypotheses for this study which is as captured below:

- Ho₁:** Asset Inspection has no significant effect on physical inventory theft fraud
- Ho₂:** Document Review has no significant effect on ghost inventory fraud
- Ho₃:** Asset Inspection has no significant effect on ghost inventory fraud
- Ho₄:** Document Review has no significant effect on physical inventory theft fraud

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework Auditing

According to Prof. L.R Dicksee (1909) Auditing is an examination of accounting records undertaken with a view to establish whether they correctly and completely reflect the transactions to which they relate, furthermore the Association of International certified public Accountant (AICPA) states that "Auditing is the process by which a competent independent person accumulates and evaluate audit evidence about quantifiable information related to specific economic entity for the purpose of determining and reporting on the degree of correspondence between the quantifiable information and established criteria.

This auditor report is embodied in an audit report which is addressed to the people who own the business such as employee's shareholders and the government at large which have commissioned the audit to the auditor to carry out their duties under the law. As highlighted earlier Jaydee Reyes (2024) notes some audit procedures which

auditors deploy during auditing, these procedures are: Inquiry, Confirmation, Observation, Inspection of Documents, Inspection of Assets, Recalculation, Reperformance among others. For this paper I shall focus on Document Review and Inspection of Assets. Mayashree Acharya (2024) highlights some types of audits, such as Internal, External, Performance, Compliance, Statutory, Operational, IRS Tax Audits, Payroll audits, Information System Audit and Forensic Audit etc.

Inventory Fraud

This study focuses on Inventory for the public sector as that pointed out by Menson (1993), who classified inventories into four broad categories namely: (1) Production inventories, which are those purchased from the market such as materials, spare parts and components manufactured in one's own company and kept as stock for use. (2) MRO inventories (maintenance, Repairs and Operating supplies) which include, Petrol, Oil and Lubricants, etc (3) Work-in-progress inventories, which are semi-finished products usually found on the factory floor in various stages of production. (4) Finished goods inventories, which are the output of the production process, ready for sale.

As pointed out above MRO in the context of Menson (1993) constitute the bulk of inventory for most government owned organizations as such budgetary provisions are made for this inventory items on annual basis, the unfortunate thing is that while these items maybe be purchased at inflated prices there is also a possibility that they may be stolen by employees of these government owned organizations, hence the issue of inventory fraud in the Nigerian Public sector. Roni (2018) notes that Theft of government property is of concern and as such this theft of inventory can happen in several ways which are: larceny schemes which refer to when an employee simply takes inventory or assets of the government without attempting to conceal the theft in the books and records. Weaver (2015) noted that Inventory is one of the hardest assets to measure and track, inventory fraud is the type of fraud which includes misrepresentation to steal inventory related items including cash. He further categorizes inventory fraud into Actual physical; Where an asset goes missing causing a smaller number of good available for sale and loss to company, and Financial Statements; misrepresenting figures in valuation to carry out fake write offs or avoid write off to mislead shareholders is also a fraud.

They are usually committed by employees with easy access to the inventory or assets. Some employees simply carry government assets away in open view of other employees. Asset Requisition and Transfer Schemes; this type of scheme takes place when a fraudster uses internal transfer paperwork to gain access to restricted assets he or she wants. This allows the i

individual to move the assets out of the restricted area. The thief then steals the assets when they are in transit. This scheme can be as simple as an employee requesting more materials than necessary for a job and then making off with the excess.

Physical Inventory Fraud

Chirantan (2019) notes that Inventory fraud involves the theft of physical inventory items and the misstatement of inventory records on a company's financial statements. According to ACFE (2016) any lack of physical security contributes to the theft of inventory, by both employees and non-employees, if items are openly available to any employee without authorization or requisition, inventory will be susceptible to theft. Noncash fraud schemes include inventory theft, are among the most common types of frauds, accounting for 19% of all asset misappropriation schemes, according to the 2016 Report to the Nations on Occupational Fraud and Abuse by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE 2016). The ACFE (2016) further goes on to categorize inventory fraud into Inventory Record Fraud and Inventory Sales and Purchases Fraud. Inventory Record Fraud consist of frauds that involve the theft of inventory items when the theft is hidden by manipulating the perpetual inventory records, it can occur through False Write-Off Schemes, False Stock Takes, Perpetual Record Schemes, False Receiving Documentation.

In Nigeria there has been an increasing trend of physical stealing of government inventories across various public institutions and tiers of government by employees in government offices, in June 2018, the Nigerian Police Kebbi State Command recovered stolen medical equipment worth N20.8 million and arrested a suspect, Faruk Zaki who is a civil servant in the state Ministry of Health. Police Public Relations Officer, Kabiru Bawa, told newsmen in Birnin Kebbi that the medical items missing from the store were worth N29.6 million. According to the Nation newspaper on 12th January 2018, the Nigerian police in Cross River arrested a staff of the state's Ministry of Education for allegedly conspiring with other ministry workers to steal a trailer load of textbooks worth millions of naira. The State Commissioner of Police, Mr Hafiz Inuwa, told newsmen in Calabar that the textbooks belong to the Ministry of Education.

Ghost Inventory Fraud

According to Matt Ellsworth (2019) Phantom inventory is inventory reported that does not exist, it is what happens when perpetual inventory (the number of items in the front and back of the store) is greater than on-shelf availability. Joannès Vermorel (2013) notes that Phantom inventory refers to goods that are recorded as available on-hand at a storage location within inventory management software, but that are not actually present,

Stitchdiary (2017) opines that whether deliberate fraud or mistaken inventory information recording, phantom inventory needs to be spotted and controlled timely to contain the corresponding potential losses. Asset Panda (2021) notes that Ghost assets are recorded as fixed assets in your business ledger, but in reality, can't be accounted for since they no longer physically exist, this discrepancy happens because, over the years, you purchase items for your business such as machinery, furniture, and equipment, but these can often disappear or depreciate for various reasons, which are an employee may steal a company computer which is still counted as fixed asset in your ledger.

Detecting and Preventing Inventory Fraud

The ACFE (2016) noted a few ways to detect and prevent inventory fraud through; Hand written alterations to documentation that do not have sufficient independent authorization; Suspicious entries in the perpetual records, particularly ones that do not fully explain the reduction in inventory. Requiring two people sign off on all such entries adds another person to the process that may prevent the theft; Shipments of stock that do not correlate to a sales invoice should raise questions, physical security should include proper documentation to gain access to relevant inventory. Limiting access to the stock room, particularly after work hours; Independent authorization of write-offs or scrapping of inventory items. This causes an extra set of eyes to be cast over the documentation; Documents from the supplier should be referenced to the invoice and documentation produced to add items into the perpetual system, *in addition* Quantities in the supplier's award letter should also be referenced; Separating duties in the affected areas (ordering, receiving and recording) should add a layer of control; Proper and verified stock-takes as they may be the only way that you will ever determine that stock is missing. Perpetual records are only an active control if they are compared against physical stock-takes on a regular basis and discrepancies are investigated; Review shipping records for matching addresses or addresses of employees, especially if a third-party shipping agent is used; Review purchases to determine whether they can all be traced to actual inventory. If the inventory items cannot be located, a purchasing scheme may have been used to steal these items.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Physical Inventory Fraud

Torky Althaqafi (2020) carried out a study on effect of Inventory Management on Financial Performance: Evidence from The Saudi Manufacturing Company: Case Study. This study explores the relationship between

inventory control and the financial performance of a particular company through the use of a case study approach. It also examines factors that draw back the process of inventory control. The results showed that the profitability of a company has a significant relationship with inventory management, and this suggests that if the management of inventory is done effectively, it ensures more profitability, while poor management translates to a poor financial performance. This study didn't consider the effect of inventory fraud on financial performance of companies, also this study focuses on the private sector in Saudi Arabia, and these gaps will be addressed in this study.

Nwadighoha (2017) carried out a study on the effect of fraud Control Mechanism on Inventory, Fund and other Related Assets of Corporate Organizations in Nigeria, multiple regression analysis with the aid e-view Watson Durbin F. Statistic which is a computerbased model was used to test various hypotheses of the study. The findings of the study showed that there is a direct and strong relationship between fraud control mechanisms on inventory, fund and other related assets of the companies under study, the study found out that there is a direct and positive relationship between fraud control mechanisms and the asset depletion of the companies under study. The study focused on the effect of fraud control mechanism on inventory, fund and other related assets of corporate organizations in Nigeria, the study did not consider the effect of forensic accounting on some specific areas of inventory fraud, and also the population of the study was drawn from the private sector, this also will be addressed in this study as the population of this study will cover the public sector in Nigeria.

Ghost Inventory Fraud

Stephen Kcheruiyot (2014) carried out a study on Effectiveness of Internal Control Systems in Safeguarding Inventory a Case Study of Rift Valley Institute of Science and Technology, the study made use of structured questionnaires for collecting data from the sample size of 187 employees which was determined through the use stratified sampling method. Spearman rank order correlation and regression analysis were used to establish the relationship between the different components of the internal control systems and the effectiveness in safeguarding inventories. The findings of this study showed that internal procurement control, stores controls, stock distribution control and management control policies were effective in safeguarding inventories at the institute.

This study focused on effectiveness of internal control systems in safeguarding inventory, it did not consider the use of forensic accounting in safeguarding inventory, as well as the effect of forensic accounting on inventory fraud, and furthermore the study derived its population from Kenya, these issues will be addressed in this

study as this study will make use of various ministries, departments and agencies in the federal capital territory Abuja – Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

White-Collar Crime Theory

Sutherland, 1949 as cited in Michael, (2004) defined White collar Crime as crime committed by a person of respectable and high social status in the course of their occupation, hence in this study, inventory fraud is seen as an occupational fraud, as this fraud is committed by those who occupy certain positions in an organization. Sutherland noted that in his time, less than 2 percent of those committed to Prison in a year belong to the upper class. He further tried to establish a relationship between money, social status, and the probability of going to jail for a white-collar crime with a more visible, typical crime. Sutherland (1949) tried to classify and define the difference between the bluecollar street crimes like burglary, theft, rape, arson and vandalism which are often blamed on psychological, associational and structural factor with white collar crimes committed by criminals who are opportunists who overtime learn that they can take advantage of their circumstances to accumulate financial gains. However, it is worthy to note that most White-Collar crimes are perpetrated through fraudulent means. These criminals are educated, intelligent, affluent individuals who can get a job which allows them unfettered and unmonitored access to often large sum of money and inventory. White collar crimes include such illegal acts which are characterize by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust and which are not necessarily dependent on the application of physical force or violence.

Fraud Triangle Theory

As highlighted by Gamlath Mohottige, Mudith Sujeewa, Mohd Shukri Ab Yajid Ali Khatibi S. M. Ferdous Azam IsuriDharmaratne (2018) in their book *The New Fraud Triangle Theory - Integrating Ethical Values of Employees* stated that Fraud Triangle as postulated by Cressey Donald, when he was working on his PhD in criminology in 1953, he decided that his dissertation would focus on embezzlers. To serve as a basis for his research, Cressey interviewed about 200 people who had been interacted for embezzling funds. He formulated the hypothesis as follows; “Trusted persons become trust violators when they conceive of themselves as having a financial problem which is non-sharable, are aware this problem can be secretly resolved by violation of the position of financial trust and are able to apply to their own conduct in that situation verbalization which enable them to adjust their conceptions of themselves as trusted

persons with their conceptions of themselves as users of the entrusted finds or property” (Cressey, 1973). Over the years, hypothesis formulated in his study has become better known as the fraud triangle. One leg of the triangle represents a Pressure, second leg represents opportunity and the final leg stands for rationalization. This study will be based on the theory of white-collar crime as put forward by Sutherland.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

For the Purpose of this study the Survey research design was used to collect primary data through the use of a structured questionnaire. The population for this study will be drawn from Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

In picking the appropriate population for this study, various Federal Government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) in federal capital territory Abuja were considered, however for the purpose of this study, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Abuja was adopted, which has a staff population of 1,542 comprising of the National Headquarters and Fct Office. In this study, a purposive sampling technique was used to select samples from the population, using the Taro Yameni method, the population will comprise of Professional Auditors, Accountants, Finance officers, Operations officers, and Store officers. The sampling technique used is the Taro Yameni method, it is shown below as

$$S = \frac{Nx^2}{1 + N(e)x^2}$$

Where

S = Sample size

N = Population of area of study

e = Estimated margin of error

1 = Theoretical constant

N= 1,542

$$S = \frac{1542}{1+1542(0.05)^2}$$

S = 317.6

≈ 318

In using purposive sampling technique, specific elements which satisfy some predetermined criteria, are selected. Thus, through purposive sampling the researcher is able to select respondents he considers knowledgeable in the subject area under investigation. A total of three hundred and fifty questionnaires were issued, with three hundred

and eighteen valid responses returned.

Method of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data collection methods were used in this study. For the primary data, a structured questionnaire was issued, while secondary data was collected from scholarly journals, publications by professional organizations, archival materials, scholars, online sources (official websites), newspapers and magazines. In using these secondary data sources relevant insight and knowledge was gained as it concerns the subject matter.

Five points rating likert scale questionnaire was used which was rated as follows: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Techniques for Data Analysis

The simple regression model was used to analyze the data collected for this study through the use of the questionnaire.

Model Specification

The model specification for this study will be as follows:

$$\text{PITF} = a + \beta \text{AI} \quad (1) \quad \text{GIF} = a + \beta \text{DR} \quad (2) \quad \text{GIF} = a + \beta \text{AI} \quad (3) \\ \text{PITF} = a + \beta \text{DR} \quad (4)$$

Where:

AI = Asset Inspection, DR = Document Review

PITF = Physical Inventory Theft Fraud, GIF = Ghost Inventory Fraud, β = Constant (Coefficient) to be estimated = a

Data Presentation and Analysis

Equation	Obs	Parms	RMSE	"R-sq"	F	P
pitf	318	2	.3929424	0.1515	21.61412	0.0000
gif	318	2	.3423243	0.1537	72.2783	0.0000
gif	318	2	.3624912	0.1272	11.13287	0.0009
pitf	318	2	.050014	0.0901	77.73438	0.0005

	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
----- pitf -----						
fora	-.184127	.0396049	-4.65	0.000	-.2619879	-.1062661
_cons	5.012063	.1768414	28.34	0.000	4.664403	5.359724
----- gif -----						
fora	.2933333	.034503	8.50	0.000	.2255023	.3611643
_cons	3.533333	.154061	22.93	0.000	3.230458	3.836208
----- gif -----						
fora	.1219048	.0365357	3.34	0.001	.0500777	.1937318
_cons	4.299048	.163137	26.35	0.000	3.97833	4.619766
----- pitf -----						
fora	-.0044444	.0050409	-0.88	0.378	-.0143546	.0054657
_cons	4.022222	.0225085	178.70	0.000	3.977972	4.066473

Firstly, the F-statistics of PITF, GIF, GIF, PITF, were 21.61412, 72.2783, 11.13287 and 77.73438, with P-values of 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0009, and 0.0005 which are all less than the 5% (0.05) significance level showing that all the models for each hypothesis are significant and fit to be used for the study to test the effect of the independent variable on each of the dependent variables.

Secondly using the R^2 , it can be observed that the R^2 values for PITF, GIF, GIF and PITF were 0.1515, 0.1537, 0.1272 and 0.0901 respectively, which implies that the variability of the dependent variables that can be accounted for by the independent variable (Asset Inspection and Document Review) are 15.15%, 15.37%, 12.72% and 15.01% respectively. The remaining can be accounted for by other factors not captured in the

regression model. Also, it can be observed that internal audit accounts for a cumulative of about 58.25% variability inventory fraud in the study area, while the remaining 41.75% can be accounted for by other variables not captured in the regression models of the study.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study has an objective to determine the effect of Internal Auditing on physical inventory theft fraud, based on the analysis of data gathered the study found a negative and insignificant effect of internal audit on physical inventory theft fraud. This means that internal auditing has an inverse but insignificant effect on physical

inventory theft fraud, such that the internal auditing practices cause an insignificantly lower occurrence of in physical inventory theft fraud in the study area. This implies that an increase or continuation in the present internal auditing practices of the study area will lead to a corresponding but insignificant decrease in physical inventory theft fraud in the study area.

One of the objectives of this study is to evaluate the effect of Internal Auditing on ghost inventory fraud; the study found a positive and significant effect of Internal Auditing on ghost inventory fraud. This means that Internal Auditing has a converse effect on ghost inventory fraud, which implies that the level or kind of internal auditing that is being carried out in the study area has resulted to a significant occurrence of ghost inventory fraud. This could among several possible reasons, be because the internal audit department or experts that have been assigned to the organisation have not been active or skilled enough to detect the ghost inventory fraud cases. This finding is consistent with that of Stephen K Cheruiyot (2014) who examined the Effectiveness of Internal Control Systems in Safeguarding Inventory a Case Study of Rift Valley Institute of Science and Technology and Nwadihoha (2017) who carried out a study on the effect of fraud Control Mechanism on Inventory, Fund and other Related Assets of Corporate Organizations in Nigeria

CONCLUSION

The study found a negative and insignificant effect of internal Auditing on physical inventory theft fraud. This finding implies that the forensic accounting that is practiced in the study area as led to a decrease in the physical inventory theft fraud but the decrease has been insignificant. The study therefore concludes that the internal auditing practiced has been fair but not excellent in curtailing and mitigating the physical inventory theft fraud in the study area.

Again, the study found a positive and significant effect of internal auditing on ghost inventory fraud, also implying that the internal auditing practiced in the study area has allowed room for a significant increase in ghost inventory fraud. The study therefore concludes here that the internal auditing practiced in the study area has not been effective enough to minimize ghost inventory fraud in the area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

i. Internal Auditing practiced has been fair but not excellent in battling the physical inventory theft fraud in

the study area, the elements that concern physical inventory theft fraud should also be improved upon by putting a little more effort for the effect to become significant. The management or leadership in the sector can enhance physical security efforts to prevent unauthorised movement of physical inventory, also deploy technological barricades as well as use of close circuit television (CCTV) with designated officers to man the system.

ii. Similarly, as others before, since the internal auditing practiced in the study area has not been effective enough to minimize ghost inventory fraud in the area, elements of the internal auditing that are aimed at minimizing ghost inventory fraud should be enhanced rigorously to ensure the fraud is mitigated. The inventory management recording mechanism should be enhanced to have software that have several ways of detecting ghost entries in order to minimize the occurrence of ghost inventory fraud. Also, regular unannounced inventory counts should be done and rotated among different officers.

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